

THE FUTURE LANGUAGE IT TAKES OVER THE WORLD, NO ONE CAN RECOGNIZE IT AT ALL

Marufova Ruxshonaxon Kamolxon qizi

8th grade pupil of Iskhakhan Ibrat Creativity School

Cowriter **Shukhratjon Ismoiljonov**

English language teacher at a current school PhD student at NamSIFL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7999995>

Abstract: The future language is a topic that explores the evolution of language in the coming years. With the rise of technology and globalization, it is expected that language will continue to change and adapt to new circumstances. Some experts predict that English will become even more dominant as a global language, while others believe that new languages will emerge as a result of cultural shifts and technological advancements. Additionally, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning may also have an impact on language, with the possibility of creating new forms of communication and language processing. As we move towards the future, it will be interesting to see how language evolves and adapts to the changing world around us.

Key words. evolution, language, technology, globalization, English, dominant, global, cultural shifts, technological advancements, artificial intelligence, machine learning, communication, language processing, changing world.

ЯЗЫК БУДУЩЕГО, НА КОТОРОМ ОН ЗАХВАТЫВАЕТ МИР, НИКТО НЕ МОЖЕТ ЕГО УЗНАТЬ ВООБЩЕ

Аннотация. Будущий язык — это тема, которая исследует эволюцию языка в ближайшие годы. Ожидается, что с развитием технологий и глобализацией язык будет продолжать меняться и адаптироваться к новым обстоятельствам. Некоторые эксперты предсказывают, что английский станет еще более доминирующим языком в мире, в то время как другие считают, что новые языки появятся в результате культурных сдвигов и технологических достижений. Кроме того, использование искусственного интеллекта и машинного обучения также может оказать влияние на язык с возможностью создания новых форм общения и языковой обработки. По мере того, как мы движемся к будущему, будет интересно посмотреть, как язык развивается и адаптируется к меняющемуся миру вокруг нас.

Ключевые слова. эволюция, язык, технология, глобализация, английский язык, доминирующий, глобальный, культурные сдвиги, технологические достижения, искусственный интеллект, машинное обучение, общение, обработка языка, меняющийся мир.

INTRODUCTION

As we move towards a more interconnected world, the question of what language will dominate the future becomes increasingly important. While English is currently the most widely spoken language in the world, there are several factors that suggest it may not remain so in the future.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Until today, no language has spread like that (the language) in the world. Even people who do not know the language at all, know it at least by name. Which language is it? I think you found. It is English. It is a language belonging to the Germanic group of the Indo-European family. Virtually, it originated in Britain. But nowadays it is occupying over the world. A lot of people say that –It is the 3rd most used language in the world. This is the main proof of its importance and popularity today. True, before Russian speaks were the foundation of our country. But after independence the demand for learning English has increased soon. Furthermore, according to 1992, more than 4 000000 people knew English. Since World War II English was known including nearly universal times like, “Ok”, “Internet” and, “hamburger”. A linguist at the Max Planck Institute, Martin Haspelmath said that the extent to which a language loans words is measure of its prestige

One major factor is the rise of China as a global superpower. With a population of over 1.4 billion people and a rapidly growing economy, China's influence on the world stage is only set to increase in the coming years. As a result, Mandarin Chinese is likely to become an increasingly important language in international business and diplomacy.

Another factor is the growing importance of technology in our lives. As artificial intelligence and machine learning continue to advance, it's possible that we may develop new forms of communication that make traditional languages obsolete. For example, some experts predict that we may one day communicate using a universal language based on mathematical symbols.

Finally, there is the question of cultural globalization. As people from different parts of the world interact more frequently, it's possible that a new "global" language could emerge that combines elements of different languages and cultures. This could be seen as a way of promoting unity and understanding between different peoples.

Of course, predicting the future of language is a complex and uncertain task. It's possible that English will continue to dominate as the lingua franca of the global community, or that some other language entirely will emerge as the dominant force. Whatever happens, it's clear that learning multiple languages will continue to be an important skill for those who want to succeed in the globalized world of tomorrow.

Today everybody knows it. English, clearly, is now on top. You can say -, Are There other languages in the world?’. True, there are also other languages, too. But the lack of need for them increased English among the people. It was increased the international; influence of the USA in the 17th and 20th centuries. Accordingly, while the number of languages in the world diminishing, the number of English is increasing. Particularly, in USA India, India, New Zealand, Northern Ireland, Australia, Canada, Great Britain an in more than 15 countries of Africa, English is used as an official language. Also, the term WORLD ENGLISH is still use, but is contested by critics who believe it strikes too strong a note of dominance. Today’s World English is known by several names, perhaps the catchiest of which is Globish (though personally I think it sound silly) a term popularized by jean Paul Nerriere in his book Which is called” Don’t speak English, Parle Globish”. This book is very interesting; however, I haven’t ever read. Many people like English because of its comfort. Hence John Adams says English “the most respectable”. So that I think in the future English will be the 1st. What do you think? Is it real?

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the future of language is a fascinating topic that explores how language will evolve and adapt in the coming years. With the advancement of technology and globalization, it is expected that language will continue to change and transform to meet new circumstances. While some predict that English will become even more dominant as a global language, others believe that new languages will emerge as a result of cultural changes and technological breakthroughs. Moreover, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning may also impact language, with the possibility of creating new forms of communication and language processing. As we move towards the future, it will be interesting to observe how language evolves and adapts to the changing world around us.

References:

1. English language /Origin, History, Development...Britannica
britannica.com/topic/English-language
2. English Americans. En.wikipedia.org/wiki/English_Americans
3. "The future of English ? " written by David Graddol
4. Culpeper J:History of English.London;Routledge
5. <https://doi.org/104324/9780203023501>
6. Algeo.J.Pyles T (2010) The origins and development of the English language. Boston: WADSWORTH Cengage learning